

SHORT AND LONG-TERM DAMAGE CHARACTERISATION: AN OPTICAL AND MECHANICAL APPROACH APPLIED TO CSM COMPOSITES AND RUBBER MODIFIED PMMA

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ABSTRACT

By the use of two different techniques of damage analysis based on the modification of the optical and mechanical properties of a material under load, it has been possible to characterise damage initiation and progression in a chopped strand mat composite (CSM) and a three layer particles rubber toughened poly(methyl methacrylate) (RTPMMA) subjected to both short and long-term tensile loading. Damage was detected by measuring the reduction in transmitted light during a monotonic tensile test as well by measuring the loss in Young's modulus during a load-unload cycle tensile test. Finally, the creep behaviour of the CSM composite has been successfully modelled using a power law relationship enabling us to construct damage development-lifetime maps.

INTRODUCTION

Among the damage modes observed in polymeric and composites materials, most of them lead to the formation of voids in the matrix or at the fibre-matrix interfaces. These voids, generated by mechanical stresses, generally take the form of crazes, microcracks and localised shearing in the RTPMMA matrix and fibre-matrix debonding in the CSM composite, which although difficult to detect, can have serious consequences on the long-term stability of the mechanical properties of the material.

In this study, an optical technique exploiting the light scattering due to the difference of refractive index between the voids created and the bulk material has been developed to characterise the process of damage initiation and development in a CSM composite and a three-layer particles rubber toughened poly(methyl methacrylate) (RTPMMA) subjected to tensile loading. This technique, in which the reduction in transmitted light is correlated with the degree of volumetric damage, offers the advantage in that damage progression can in principle be followed in-situ without unloading or removing the specimen [2]. In the case of a CSM laminate, the damage initiation and development during short-term test has been subsequently quantified by a cyclic load-unload test, in which the decrease of modulus is correlated with the corresponding applied strain [1]. The two techniques yield a similar value for the damage threshold strain in this material and, via a simple calibration curve, the optical damage monitored in-situ during short-term tests has been correlated with the loss in mechanical properties.

The amount of mechanical damage occurring during creep tests was quantified by measuring the loss of Young's modulus before testing and after creep loading. The results obtained from the creep study were then compared with the data obtained during short-term load-unload tests. The creep response of the composite has been modelled by applying a power law to the data. The

variation of the power law coefficients with applied stress and test temperature were determined, allowing a prediction of the long-term response of the material for each thermo-mechanical loading condition.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The tests conducted in this study were undertaken on DERAKANE* 411-45 epoxy vinyl ester resin-based chopped strand mat composites and a rubber-toughened PMMA supplied by Atochem. Laminates of nominal thickness two millimetres were manufactured by stacking (usually three) 300g/m² powder bonded E-glass chopped strand mats (Owens Corning Fiberglass), impregnating by hand rolling and compressing between two steel plates. All of the laminates were moulded at room temperature and then subsequently post-cured for five hours at 100°C. The nominal fibre weight fraction in each case was approximately thirty percent.

The PMMA matrix with a molecular weight average (M_w) of 130'000 g/mol and a T_g of ~115°C was toughened by three-layer particles with a PMMA core, surrounded by an inner shell of crosslinked butyl acrylate-co-styrene and an outer shell of PMMA, with an overall diameter of 250 nm. Samples were provided in the form of 3 mm thick plaques with global particle volume fractions of 30%.

Mechanical Tests

Quasi-static tests (monotonic and cyclic tensile tests) and tensile creep tests were undertaken on dog-bone specimens (ASTM D638MI) having a working section of 50 x 10 x 2-3 mm. The variation of strain during short-term tests was measured over a 50 mm section using a mechanical extensometer with a precision of five microns. Loading and unloading was undertaken at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/minute. The creep strain was measured by bonding a 50 mm long strain gauge to the centre of the specimen. The strain response of the specimen was measured using a computer-controlled UPM60 data logger and all relevant information was stored on a Macintosh computer using Labview facilities.

Experimental Set-up

Optical damage development during both the short and the long-term tests was assessed by measuring the reduction in the intensity of transmitted light during the test. Initially a Canon Ci 20PM camera was placed approximately one meter in front of the specimen and a diffused white light source directly behind it. The resulting images were analysed by computer using the Optilab® (Graftek) image analysis system and Labview facilities. Figure 1 shows the optical sequence obtained for the CSM composite. The average value of the different levels of grey was then correlated with the damage development. This system, although giving relevant information, needed an important logistic for analysis and did not permit the following of long-term tests. This was subsequently possible by replacing the camera with a photovoltaic detector UDT-555UV, where the initial voltage intensity was controlled by an offset and the resulting loss of transmitted light was associated with the resulting decrease of voltage amplified to a 0-10V range. By carefully positioning the extensometer, the light source, and the photodetector, Fig. 2, it was possible to relate directly the degree of mechanical damage to the reduction in transmitted light.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Short-Term Tests

In order to correlate the change in the level of transmitted light during a test with the degree of volumetric damage, an optical damage parameter, D_1 , was defined as follows:

$$D_1(\varepsilon, \sigma, t) = 1 - \frac{I_{\text{transmitted}}}{I_{\text{transmitted,max}}} \quad (1)$$

Damage development during a cyclic tensile test was quantified by the reduction in Young's modulus. A damage parameter, D , represents this reduction. The damage in the (n-1)th cycle, D_n , is related to the corresponding modulus E_n and the initial modulus E_0 by the relationship:

$$D_n(\varepsilon, \sigma, t) = 1 - \frac{E_n}{E_0} \quad (2)$$

Epoxy E-Glass CSM Composite

As shown in Figure 3 for the CSM laminate, the measurement of the transmitted light during a monotonic tensile test yields a damage threshold strain of 0.48% and a maximum value of D_1 at sample failure of 42%. These results were correlated by the cyclic load-unload approach, which gave a similar damage threshold strain parameter and a damage development rate of 8.7%/‰ by applying an experimental conditions dependant ratio of 6 between y-scale of D and D_1 . Here it was then possible to quantify mechanical damage initiation and development simply by measuring the reduction in transmitted light during short-term monotonic tensile tests.

Distinct regimes in the optical damage process were detected. Initially, one can observe a stability in transmitted light corresponding to a zero damage during the elastic response of the material. Following this, damage initiation is observed corresponding to fracture of fibre-matrix interface situated at 90° to the applied load. Finally, failure occurs at interfaces oriented at angles between 90° and approximately 45° to the applied load. Figure 4(a) shows the intralaminar crack propagation observed in this third phase. During these two regimes, damage occurs first in high fibre concentration zones, where stress concentration is important and stress relaxation at matrix-fibre interfaces is limited.

Rubber-Toughened PMMA

In this material, the determination of a given damage threshold strain is a little bit more complex due to the simultaneous development of the different damage processes and to the difficulty to identify and to differentiate their own influences by a simple optical measurement. As depicted by Plummer [3] in thin films, damage initiation in a three-layer particles happens initially in the zones rich in clusters of particles. It comes from cavitation of the rubber shell around its whole circumference providing effective nucleation sites for crazes. The created voids are separated by ligaments of rubber linking the glass outer shell/matrix to the glass inner core, Fig 4(b). Considering the minimum wavelength of the light spectrum (240 nm), these damage phenomena must not interfere with incident light but can however reduce its intensity by absorption. As deformation continues, there is widespread crazing in the intervening matrix regions and the particles are incorporated within the deformed regions of matrix, becoming highly elongated. This crazes propagation can be considered as the predominant source of light scattering and the principal cause for the decrease of the Young's modulus. Figure 5 shows the correspondence between the optical damage initiation and the loss of linearity in the elastic domain at 1.4 % strain. All light intensity-strain curves exhibited a maximum damage rate corresponding closely to yield strain (5 % strain) and an asymptotic form suggesting that optical damage tends towards an upper bound in which it is impossible to continue damaging the material indefinitely. Within large clusters, the dominant deformation mode appears to be homogeneous shear banding rather

than crazing, with matrix fibrillation tending to occur beyond regions of high particle density. This explains the macroscopically visible 45° shear bands.

Long-Term Tests, Power Law Model

In order to study the viscoelastic behaviour of the CSM composite, creep tests at stress between 20 and 90% of the failure strength have been undertaken at room temperature and 80°C. Previous studies [4,5,6] have shown that a power law relationship based upon Shapery's theory can predict with some considerable success the linear or non-linear viscoelastic creep response of both isotropic and anisotropic materials. Considering the stress in the matrix as an independent variable, the non-linear viscoelastic constitutive equation derived by Shapery for an isotropic material under isothermal conditions and uniaxial loading can be written:

$$\epsilon(t) = g_0 D_0 \sigma(t) + g_1 \int_0^t \Delta D(\Psi - \Psi') \frac{d}{d\tau} [g_2 \sigma(t)] d\tau \tag{3}$$

Where D_0 and $\Delta D(\Psi)$ are respectively the linear elastic and the transient components of the compliance, τ is a dummy variable of integration, Ψ and Ψ' are the so-called reduced-times and $g_0, g_1, g_2(\sigma, T, \%H_2O)$, and $a_\sigma(\sigma, T, \%H_2O, t)$ are non-linearizing material parameters. In case of linear viscoelastic behaviour, g_0, g_1, g_2 take unit value, and creep strain at constant load σ_a can be written as a power law relationship of the form:

$$\epsilon_c(t) = [D_0 + C(t^n - 1)] \sigma_a \tag{4}$$

Where C and n must be parameters independent of stress level and time calculated by a least-squares fitting of experimental data. By plotting the log of the creep rate as a function of time, the linearity of the experimental data over the entire period suggests that the linear viscoelastic model can successfully predict the creep strain of this material. Table 1 gives the calculated values of D_0, C and n.

Temperature [°C]	Stress [MPa]	m [sec ⁻¹]	D ₀ [GPa ⁻¹]	C [Pa ⁻¹ *sec ⁻¹]	n [-]
20	20	1.09E-03	1.13E-02	5.47E-11	2.36E-01
	30	4.42E-03	1.21E-02	1.47E-10	1.87E-01
	40	4.59E-03	1.26E-02	1.15E-10	1.73E-01
	50	4.01E-02	1.23E-02	8.03E-10	1.02E-01
	60	1.02E-01	1.28E-02	1.69E-09	7.52E-02
	70	1.63E-01	1.36E-02	2.33E-09	6.73E-02
	80	2.06E-01	1.39E-02	2.58E-09	6.70E-02
	90	2.84E-01	1.44E-02	3.15E-09	5.99E-02
80	20	1.62E-02	1.12E-02	8.09E-10	1.35E-01
	30	6.84E-02	1.36E-02	2.28E-09	9.40E-02
	40	1.35E-01	1.37E-02	3.37E-09	8.50E-02
	50	2.70E-01	1.62E-02	5.40E-09	7.05E-02
	60	4.16E-01	1.55E-02	6.93E-09	5.39E-02
	80	1.11E+00	1.69E-02	1.38E-08	4.00E-02

Tab. 1: Power Law Parameters determined after 40 day creep tests

Although theoretically stress independent, the parameters obtained, C and n, vary strongly above the stress damage threshold. This suggests that creep response of CSM composite is not only generated by the matrix viscoelastic deformation but is also strongly affected by the

damage development due to fibre-matrix debonding. The amount of damage incurred during creep testing was quantified by measuring the modulus before testing and after creep loading for forty days followed by recovery. The degree of damage was then correlated with the creep strain measured just prior to unloading. Previous work [2] showed that creep damage data fell on the same curve as the short-term results and that the maximum strain determined the amount of damage in this material. Therefore, from a knowledge of the creep strain history of the damage threshold strain and of the failure strain, one can, in principle, construct damage development-lifetime maps over the range of temperatures and applied loads for prediction of failure and determination of realistic design loading conditions to avoid damage initiation during the lifetime of the component (Fig.6).

CONCLUSIONS

The optical technique offers the advantage in that damage can in principle be monitored in situ during short-time tests without unloading or removing the specimen. A similar value of damage onset has been observed in the CSM composite using load cycling test technique as well as the optical approach. Via a simple calibration curve, the optical damage has been correlated with the loss in mechanical properties. Contrary to the CSM composite, the measurement of the level of transmitted light during the test for the RMPMMA did not allow for the identification of the damage processes. Because of their complexity and their simultaneity, their succeeding and their proper influence on the mechanical properties of the material stay difficult to characterise. Nevertheless, a damage threshold has been determined. In using a power law relationship, the creep response of the CSM composite has been successfully modelled. From a knowledge of the damage threshold and the failure strain, damage development-lifetime maps have been subsequently constructed.

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Figure 1. Subsequent steps of the optical damage development during the elastic (A) and the non-linear domain (B) of a tensile test and after breakage (C) of the sample.

Figure 2. Experimental set-up

Figure 3. Correlation between damage initiation and development determined during a monotonic tensile test followed optically [$D_1 = 1 - (I_{\text{transmitted}}/I_{\text{maximum}})$] and during a cyclic load-unload tensile tests [$D = 1 - (E_r/E_0)$].

Figure 4(a). Intralaminar crack propagation.
SEM 650x

Figure 4(b). Large deformation in a 0.3 μm microtomed film containing three-layer particles 40% observed by TEM at 100kV.

Figure 5. Damage initiation and development determined during a monotonic tensile test followed optically [$D_1 = 1 - (I_{\text{transmitted}}/I_{\text{maximum}})$] on a three-layer particles rubber toughened PMMA.

Figure 6. Damage development-lifetime map, data from 40 days creep tests at different stress level. Tests temperature 23°C.